

E-LEARNING: IMPACT ON STUDENT'S ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO MANGALURU CITY

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Abstract

Today's generation is accustomed to using internet learning in addition to face-to-face training. The phrase "E-learning," which refers to the initial acquisition, use, diffusion, and facilitation of knowledge by electronic methods, has evolved with the growth of information and communications technology. Actually, the growth in its use is directly correlated with the number of students. Since it has been proven that interactive, multimedia-rich information has a significant impact on learning, educators are working very hard to help pupils acquire it. Researchers have also examined how blogs and wikis affect students' ability to reflect and collaborate, and both results have been positive. According to the UNESCO Global Education Monitoring Report of 2020, technology is significant. The goal of this study is to understand how e-learning affects students' academic performance and to identify strategies for making e-learning resources more accessible to improve students' academic performance. Methodology used was collection of primary data from the students of a Mangaluru college and review of the literature, published articles are the secondary data. The results indicate that majority of respondents are happy with the objectives and scope of online learning, as well as how well it advances learner-learner interaction and improves respondents' knowledge.

Keywords: E Learning, face to face training, multimedia, UNESCO, information and communication.

INTRODUCTION

A formalised teaching-based learning approach that uses electronic resources is called "e-learning." While education can occur in or outside of formal classroom settings, e-learning is primarily focused on using computers and the Internet.

E-learning, commonly referred to as a network-enabled transfer of skills and knowledge, is the dissemination of education to numerous recipients simultaneously or over a period of time. It wasn't properly acknowledged earlier because it was believed that this approach lacked the human element required for learning. E-learning has solidified its place and altered the educational landscape a year after the COVID-19 pandemic. Electronic learning seeks to make it possible for students to learn without being physically present in a classroom by providing improved organisation and top-notch courses.

Psychologists also believe that this audio-visual approach to teaching engages students well. It can fit all learning methods and is versatile. According to the UNESCO Global Education Monitoring Report of 2020, technology is significant. The study shows how much technology's potential to support inclusive education is yet unrealized.

The Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology acknowledges the importance of electronic education as a tool for delivering education. Technology advancement has increased the accessibility of information.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Mikilesh Prakash Yadav, Madhu Arora, Sunil Kumara and Sanjay Nandal, 2020, Numerous pupils have previously been proven to be receptive to adopting digital media for learning, according to study. There is also no obvious distinction in this aspect between the various groups. respectively, rural, urban, and metropolitan. In terms of smartphone accessibility, nearly identical findings were made. Therefore, the smart phone is not a major issue with digital learning, but in terms of understanding, rural students are more comfortable with traditional lecturers than urban and suburban students who are already used to getting digital lectures earlier. Therefore, by exposing students to real-world examples of digital media, efforts should be made to boost the usefulness of this medium as a tool for learning.

Daniel brian 2020, In his investigations, Daniel Brian claims that e-learning has reduced a number of learning-related issues, including time and money issues that previously limited students' learning options. These justifications are sufficient to support the idea that while e-

learning offers a solution to many significant learning issues, it shouldn't be limited to academic settings solely.

Sumit Goyal (2012), claims that his research shows that the idea of e-Learning is becoming increasingly popular these days because so many colleges are now providing degree and diploma programmes in an e-Learning format. Like Reliance and Tata Steel, many large corporations are making investments in e-Learning and establishing their interactive classrooms. To produce e-Learning modules, subject matter experts are creating new, flexible technologies. ILT in educational settings is reflected in the weight of the backpacks that students must carry and the back discomfort they experience since fewer and fewer trees are being planted as a result of the felling of trees for the production of rubber, paper, pencils, and other goods. In the current era of modernization, it would be a more alluring, pleasurable, and considerate choice to take it if each learner were provided a tablet with the course material already loaded onto it.

M. Samir Abou El-Seoud , Islam A.T.F. Taj-Eddin , Naglaa Seddiek, Mahmoud M. El-Khouly , Ann Nosseir (2014), When instructing online courses, instructors must comprehend the motivations of their students. The fact that additional technology does not always result in improved learning results should be recognised. Evaluating e-learning and its consequences for raising the calibre of teaching and learning through e-learning should be the main topics of the interview questions.

Computer-based training (CBT) is typically multimedia-based instruction, according to Zahm (2000), and is typically given through CD-ROM or as a Web download. Any well-designed computer-based training, whether it is network-based or provided over the Internet, is more convenient than conventional instructor-led training or seminars, according to Karon (2000), who explored the convenience aspect of computer-based training. Self-paced CBT courses are accessible whenever learners are prepared to take them, not simply when the seminar is scheduled or the instructor is available, continued Karon. By highlighting computer-based training as an all-inclusive phrase used to represent any computer-delivered training, including CD-ROM and the World Wide Web, Hall (1997) combined both Zahm (2000) and Karon (2000) definitions. Hall went on to say that some individuals use the term CBT to refer only to old-time, text-only training.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The study aims to achieve the following objectives.

- To identify the various e learning tools that are available.
- To find out ways to make e-learning tools more accessible so that students perform better academically.

Methodology

Data for this study were gathered from primary and secondary sources.

- **PRIMARY DATA**

Primary data is information that is gathered directly from the original source with the intention of introducing statistical variance. This information is fresh or previously unpublished data that was gathered directly from the source as part of a research endeavour. As primary sources of data, a questionnaire and interviews conducted were employed in the Mangaluru city. There are 126 respondents in the sample.

- **SECONDARY DATA**

Data that has already been gathered and is easily accessible from other sources is referred to as secondary data. It was gathered from a variety of publications, periodicals, websites, research files, online articles, and E books.

CONCEPTUAL WORK

After the pandemic, there was a sudden change to electronic learning, which has provided pupils with countless benefits. Electronic education is recognised by the Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology as a crucial instrument for education delivery. Information is now more readily available because to technological innovation. E Learning meets all of the demands of the students, Updated Content and Quick session transmission. One of the main benefits of e-learning is that it aids in the development of advanced abilities in both students and teachers.

E LEARNING TOOLS

It can be difficult, but it's crucial, to keep up with new, cutting-edge e-learning tools. You can create a strong e-learning plan by perusing the most recent technological developments in a range of industries. The "must-have" e-learning technologies include automation and

responsiveness, and gamification is one of several buzzwords that are popular in e-learning. The 10 popular e-learning tools that can be useful are

1. Automation

Automated course writing tools and automation will be the future of e-learning. These cutting-edge tools have reduced development costs and timelines. Trainers can develop new tactics that better suit students' preferences after using automation to discover how pupils learn.

2. Wearable E-Learning Tools

New trends in the e-learning sector are being driven by wearable technologies. Among the popular e-learning wearables are Google Glass and the Apple Watch.

When using Google Glass, for instance, students can access supplementary materials while learning thanks to features like Head Up Display (HUD). Live feeds allow instructors to keep an eye on their pupils' progress.

The e-learning community will change as a result of the rise of VR. In an emergency situation, students can safely practise job abilities that may be dangerous. By reducing learning risk, VR makes e-learning a safer alternative.

3. Online Video

Videos are an effective approach to study because YouTube ranks as the second-largest search engine. Online video platforms are being adopted by businesses all around the world for e-learning. Videos will continue to be a potent e-learning tool, from new hire videos to specialised training packages.

4. Gamification

A TalentLMS survey on gamification found that about 75% of workers are casual gamers. Because of this, gamification is a crucial e-learning technique. Games' leader boards, badge systems, and point systems link players to growth initiatives.

5. Responsive Design

E-learning is now available on smart devices thanks to learning management systems (LMSs). Users can experience the best readability on mobile smartphones because to their reactivity. Receptive e-learning tools are now more crucial than ever because of the surge in Bring Your Own Device (BYOD) in the workplace. Actually, 83 percent of mobile consumers emphasise the value of a unified user experience across all platforms.

A responsive mobile web design that enables employees to access learning resources, modules, and materials while on the go will maximise the effectiveness of e-learning.

6. A More Secure Cloud

It's big news for e-learning because the cloud has lately undergone a thorough security makeover. Organizations concerned about cybercrime used the cloud more securely as a result of the cloud security advancements. These firms are currently utilising the cloud to provide unmatched accessibility to e-learning.

7. Massive Online Open Courses

Massive Online Open Courses, or MOOCs, are by no means a recent development in the e-learning sector. However, businesses are finally recognising their potential contribution to team development. Numerous MOOCs that collaborate with prestigious colleges give respectable certifications.

8. Application Programming Interface

Complete compatibility is provided through Application Programming Interface (API) between various e-learning platforms. It keeps track of academic achievement by enabling cross-platform communication across applications.

9. Analytics

E-learning platforms may tailor every area of their operations thanks to the priceless information obtained through analytics. User experience is being improved by this trend. Technology facilitates analytics by providing information on learner preferences, page departure rates, time spent on particular courses, and the success of your e-learning marketing plan. Key metrics are also included in LMSs as part of the learning platform. You may assess learner skills, ratings, and progress with an LMS to strengthen your e-learning platform.

10. Personalization

With personalised e-learning, users can select their own courses and work through each component of the curriculum at their own pace. Traditional approaches cannot offer the same level of adaptability and customisation as personalised e-learning.

There are undoubtedly many options available for e-learning technologies. You are not required to pick just one, though. Many e-learning solutions are available for trial use, so you can choose the one that works best for your business. By utilising these 10 popular tools, you may effectively promote e-learning.

E-LEARNING DELIVERY METHODS

Technology has made it possible to create a variety of eLearning delivery strategies to meet the needs and preferences of learners. Here are a few typical e-learning delivery strategies.

1. Computer-Based Training or Web-Based Training

Learners can access content in computer-based training (CBT) through media like CDs and DVDs. CBT often operates on the learner's computer. On the other hand, web-based training (WBT) makes use of the internet as a platform. In WBT methodologies, learning management systems are frequently employed. Courses are self-paced and there is no interaction between instructors and students with either CBT or WBT. Adult learners who desire to learn new abilities often find these delivery techniques to be effective. (Soni, 2015)

2. Blended eLearning

Face-to-face training and computer-mediated instruction are combined in blended eLearning (Bonk & Graham, 2005). Technology like collaborative software, web-based software, and communication software is added to in-person training in this technique. Oye et al. (2012) assert that blended eLearning promotes educational and information review outside of the classroom. According to Littlejohn and Pegler (2007), blended e-learning makes it easier to combine several learning environments and provides scheduling flexibility for learners.

3. Mobile eLearning

Sharples (2000) asserts that the availability of cutting-edge mobile technology, such as wireless and high bandwidth infrastructure, has also facilitated the expansion of eLearning towards mobile eLearning. Handheld computing devices are employed in this e-learning strategy to enable access to instructional resources and information sources. Even though mobile devices are readily available and reasonably priced, this technique must take into account the mobile devices' disc capacity, screen size, and Internet connectivity capabilities (Soni, 2015).

Despite these worries, a 2019 study by Learning House indicated that 29% of college students utilise their mobile devices for at least some of the tasks associated with their courses.

4. Social eLearning

Applying social learning principles to the electronic learning process is what social eLearning entails. Social learning involves learning from and with others, as its name suggests. Direct

touch, such as face-to-face conversations, and indirect contact both have the potential to cause this (e.g., interactions on social media and discussion forums). Chetia (2019) asserts that social learning takes place when people pay attention to the actions or results of others.

According to this approach, social eLearning involves using technology like videoconferencing and social networking sites to encourage interactions between students. Along the way of learning, group discussions and question-and-answer sessions also promote social connection (Aubron, 2018).

5. Game-Based eLearning

Game-based eLearning is "the use of a computer game-based strategy to offer, assist, and enhance teaching, learning, assessment, and evaluation," according to Connolly and Stansfield (2006). Games used for online learning are made with specific learning objectives in mind and are very interactive to promote total immersion and participation. According to Chieta (2019), gamification differs from gamified eLearning in that the former uses game mechanics and aspects to make learning engaging, whilst the latter uses full-fledged games to aid learners in achieving their goals.

DIFFERENT E-LEARNING PLATFORMS

An eLearning platform is a website or portal for educational materials and content that provides students with all the information they require in one location, including lectures, resources, chances to interact with other students, and more. Additionally, it's a great tool for both the student and the teacher to keep track of a student's development.

1. Udemy

Udemy passionately believes that by making it possible for anyone and everyone to learn from its pool of more than 20000 Subject Matter Experts, this can disrupt and democratise the educational ecosystem. In a very large way, Udemy has accomplished its goal. Text and video information can be combined to develop and publish courses using the many content production tools available on this eLearning platform, including PDF and PowerPoint presentations. Instructors can use this online learning environment without paying a fee. However, Udemy earns a lot of money by keeping 50% of the proceeds from your course sales. More than 12 million people use Udemy.

2. Skillshare:

Without a question, Udemy is a fantastic online training resource. But the freedom of the educators is limited. For instance, Udemy prohibits teachers from setting course branding and pricing. Additionally, teachers know nothing about their students. Teachable made the most of all these restrictions. More than 3 million students, 7500 teachers, and 20,000 courses are available on Teachable at this time. The numbers are increasing and improving. There should be a monthly cost for instructors to use this platform. This eLearning platform offers a free eBook to draw potential customers that thoroughly discusses topics like course building, video creation, slide presentations, etc.

3. Coursera:

To offer authentic learning opportunities that have a connection to advantages in the real world, the platform collaborates with over 200 universities and businesses. Some certificates or degrees can even be earned fully through Coursera, with the potential to result in professional advantages like pay increases, job promotions, and more. Coursera offers hard and fascinating programmes on a variety of topics, so you can explore interests you may not have had previously, even if you're not searching for professional development reasons. To offer authentic learning opportunities that have a connection to advantages in the real world, the platform collaborates with over 200 universities and businesses. Some certificates or degrees can even be earned fully through Coursera, with the potential to result in professional advantages like pay increases, job promotions, and more. Coursera offers hard and fascinating programmes on a variety of topics, so you can explore interests you may not have had previously, even if you're not searching for professional development reasons.

4. Mindvalley:

One of the top platforms for personal development and change is Mindvalley. Its objective is to enable students to achieve professional success while also releasing all of their physical, mental, and spiritual potential. The people who desire to quickly enhance many aspects of their lives are most suited for Mindvalley. In Mindvalley's library, there are more than 50 courses (or quests), all taught by leading authorities in their professions, including CEOs of sizable corporations, best-selling authors, celebrity coaches, well-known therapists and business owners, and prominent international speakers. Different categories have been established for the quests, including Mind, Body, Soul, Career, Entrepreneurship, Relationships, Kids, Teens, and Parenting, as well as Performance. Each quest lasts 30 to 50 days and is often completed in less than 20 minutes every day.

5. Brilliant.org:

STEM subjects—Science, Math, and Computer Science—are the main focus of the online learning platform Brilliant. Both adults and children (who are at least 10 years old) can take the courses. Brilliant is one of the greatest learning platforms, especially for young adults, because they strive to make learning enjoyable, interesting, and interactive. Algebra, logic, advanced mathematics, calculus, geometry, classical physics, quantum mechanics, foundational computer science, and other topics are among the many courses you can master on Brilliant. Brilliant offers annual and monthly subscriptions that give users complete access to all of the platform's courses as well as a huge number of practise tests on a variety of subjects.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

RESPONDENTS INTERESTED IN E LEARNING: The study shows that, out of 128 respondents, 75% are interested in taking part in e-learning, while 25% are not interested.

ACCESSION OF SMARTPHONE, TABLET, LAPTOP, OR COMPUTER: The study shows that, out of 128 respondents, 99.2% own a smartphone, tablet, laptop, or computer, while 0.8% do not.

THE OBJECTIVES AND SPAN OF E-LEARNING LESSONS ARE CLEARLY DEFINED: The study shows that, out of 128 respondents, 42.2% of students are neutral that the objectives and span of e-Learning lessons are clearly defined., while 1.6% strongly disagree.

ONLINE PLATFORM USED BY THE STUDENTS: The study shows that, out of 128 respondents, 59.4% have opted coursera courses, while 1.6% have opted mindvalley courses.

FREQUENCY OF STUDENTS CONTACT WITH THEIR TEACHER ONE-TO-ONE: The study shows that, out of 128 respondents, 36.7% of students contact their teacher sometimes, while 0.8% don't.

UNDERSTANDIBILITY OF PRACTICAL COURSES THROUGH E-LEARNING: The study shows that, out of 128 respondents, 62.5% of students understand practical courses through eLearning, while 37.5% don't.

SATISFACTORY OF THE CONTENT PROVIDED THROUGH E-LEARNING: The study shows that, out of 128 respondents, 46.9% felt the content provided was satisfactory, while 0.8% were highly dissatisfied.

DEVELOPMENT OF PROBLEM-SOLVING SKILLS THROUGH E-LEARNING AMONG STUDENTS: The study shows that, out of 128 respondents, 53.9% are neutral about development of problem-solving skills, while 3.9% Strongly agree and strongly disagree.

E-LEARNING COURSES SATISFIES OBJECTIVES OF STUDENTS: The study shows that, out of 128 respondents, 45.3% are satisfied with the course neutrally, while 1.6% strongly agree.

ONLINE COURSES HELPS TO AID FUTURE ENDEAVOURS: The study shows that, out of 128 respondents, 47.7% of students agree that online courses help in future, while 3.1% strongly agree.

AVAILABILITY OF E-LEARNING RESOURCES: The study shows that, out of 128 respondents, 47.7% of students agree that E learning resources were easily available, while 3.1% strongly disagree.

GLOBAL ACCESSIBILITY BY E-LEARNING: The study shows that, out of 128 respondents, 46.1% of students agree that E-learning makes them able to access global world, while 2.3% strongly disagree.

ENHANCEMENT OF STUDENT'S KNOWLEDGE THROUGH E-LEARNING TOOLS: The study shows that, out of 128 respondents, 46.9% of students agree that E-learning tools enhance student's knowledge, while 2.3% strongly disagree.

E-LEARNING MOTIVATES STUDENTS'S TO DO THEIR WORK INDEPENDENTLY: The study shows that, out of 128 respondents, 38.3% of students agree that E-learning motivates them to do their work independently, while 0.8% strongly disagree.

E-LEARNING PROMOTES LEARNER-LEARNER INTERACTION: The study shows that, out of 128 respondents, 40.6% of students neutral that E-learning promotes learner-learner interaction, while 3.1% strongly disagree.

E-LEARNING PROVIDES A SATISFACTORY LEARNING EXPERIENCE: The study shows that, out of 128 respondents, 44.5% of students are neutral that e-courses provides a satisfactory learning experience, while 6.3% strongly disagree and strongly agree.

THE USE OF E-COURSES ACCELERATE LEARNING : The study shows that, out of 128 respondents, 41.4% of students are neutral that the use of e-courses accelerates learning, while 3.1% strongly disagree.

COURSE SELECTED FROM DIFFERENT PLATFORMS FROM RESPONDENTS

- a. Digital Marketing
- b. Psychology
- c. Fire & Industrial Safety
- d. Soft Skills
- e. MS Word
- f. Philosophy
- g. Forensic science
- h. Essay writing
- i. Intelligence and management
- j. Data Analysis
- k. Java, Python, Excel, C, C++, CSS & HTML
- l. Economics
- m. Graphic Designing
- n. Artificial Intelligence
- o. Data Analysis
- p. Public speaking
- q. Spanish
- r. UI/UX
- s. Content Writing
- t. Cyber security
- u. Food Processing
- v. Financial Markets
- w. French and programming
- x. Modern Learning Management Solutions
- y. Learning Dog Behaviour

z. Basic Korean language

SUGGESTIONS:

- a. Online courses must be offered at a lower cost so that the most students can benefit from them.
- b. The offered courses must be certified.
- c. Colleges should use blended learning so that students can learn in a variety of settings.
- d. Online platforms should have explicit contact information for professors.
- e. Online platforms should include a capable customer service representative to respond to students' questions as soon as possible.
- f. Online platforms must deliver credentials and results promptly.
- g. Online platforms should offer chances for internships in the relevant fields.
- h. The Rubrics for evaluation should be clearly stated and communicated to the learners.

CONCLUSION

E-learning involves more than just a shift in technology. It is a component of redefining how our species imparts knowledge, abilities, and values to future workers and students.

It is clear from the study that the majority of respondents are satisfied with the goals and scope of online learning, satisfied with the content of e learning, enhances respondents' knowledge, and promotes learner-learner interaction. Respondents do, however, encounter some issues when taking online courses. The e-learning platforms that are available to them so they can enrol in courses should be known to the students.

E-learning is here to stay and will likely have a bigger impact on higher education in the future. However, there are some drawbacks to taking classes online, including the time commitment and lack of true face-to-face connection between students and teachers. Finally, e-learning offers a promising future, amazing learning potential, and a great corporate culture.

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